

Pleomorphic Adenoma of the Left Submandibular Gland in a Female Patient. Case Report

Ortiz- Rodriguez Luis A.¹, Cisneros-Rodríguez Gilberto.¹, Guzman Chacon Edd I.¹, Rodriguez-Becerra Jesus M.¹, Zecua Mellado Yemdiel .¹, Rosales-Jimenez Jose E.¹

¹Department of General Surgery, High Specialty Medical Unit Number 25 (UMAE 25), National Medical Center of the Northeast, Mexican Institute of Social Security (IMSS), Monterrey, Nuevo León, México.

ABSTRACT

Salivary gland neoplasms represent less than 5% of head and neck tumors, with pleomorphic adenoma being the most frequent benign neoplasm. It has a higher incidence in the parotid gland (60–70%) and in the submandibular gland (10%), with a 6% risk of malignancy. Its etiology is multifactorial, including genetic predisposition, radiation, and exposure to carcinogens. Clinically, it presents as a slow-growing, painless, and well-defined mass. Diagnosis is based on imaging studies and complemented with fine-needle aspiration biopsy (FNAB), which in this case classified the lesion as Milan 4a. We present a 59-year-old female patient with a 20 cm submandibular tumor, without invasion of adjacent structures, managed with complete surgical resection. The postoperative course was favorable, and the histopathological study confirmed pleomorphic adenoma with no signs of malignancy. Surgery is the treatment of choice to prevent recurrences or malignant transformation, emphasizing the importance of early diagnosis and appropriate surgical planning.

KEYWORDS :Salivary gland tumor, uncertain behavior, pleomorphic adenoma, parotid gland, biopsy, histopathology, surgery, case report.

ABBREVIATIONS: Numeric Pain Rating Scale (NPRS), Computed Tomography (CT), Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI), Ultrasound (US), Fine-Needle Aspiration Biopsy (FNAB), Hounsfield Units (HU).

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INTRODUCTION

Submandibular gland neoplasms represent approximately 10–15% of salivary gland tumors and have a higher malignancy rate compared to parotid gland tumors, reaching up to 50% (1,2). Their etiology is multifactorial, including genetic factors, exposure to ionizing radiation, and other environmental factors such as smoking and exposure to industrial carcinogens (3,4). Among benign tumors, pleomorphic adenoma is the most frequent, accounting for 40–60% of neoplasms in this gland. Although benign, it carries a 6% risk of malignant transformation, highlighting the importance of timely diagnosis and treatment (5,6).

Clinically, these neoplasms usually present as a progressively enlarging submandibular mass, generally painless in early stages. However, in advanced cases, they may cause symptoms associated with compression of adjacent

structures, including pain, dysphagia, and paresthesia when neural involvement exists (7,8). Diagnosis is based on clinical, imaging, and cytopathological correlation, with FNAB being a key tool for lesion classification (9,10). Complementary methods such as CT and MRI allow evaluation of tumor extension and rule out locoregional involvement (11).

The management of submandibular tumors depends on their histological nature. In the case of benign lesions, complete surgical excision is the treatment of choice, as inadequate resection increases the risk of recurrence or malignant transformation (12). For malignant tumors, treatment is supplemented with radiotherapy and, in some cases, adjuvant chemotherapy to improve locoregional control (13,14). This article presents the case of a 59-year-old female patient with progressive growth in the left submandibular region. Imaging

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studies showed a well-defined mass, and FNAB classified the lesion as Milan 4a. Complete surgical resection was performed, revealing a 20 cm tumor without invasion of adjacent structures. The postoperative course was uneventful, and the histopathological study confirmed pleomorphic adenoma without signs of malignancy.

This case highlights the importance of early diagnosis and proper surgical approach in submandibular neoplasms. Clinical, imaging, and cytopathological correlation is essential for optimal management, allowing precise surgical planning and reducing the risk of complications. Literature review reinforces the need for a multidisciplinary approach in the management of these neoplasms, ensuring the best oncological and functional outcomes for the patient (15).

CASE REPORT

A 59-year-old female patient, with no history of chronic-degenerative diseases or relevant pathological history.

The condition began seven years prior with the presence of increased volume in the left cervical region, at the middle third of the neck, without associated pain, skin discoloration, or other accompanying symptoms. The patient initially consulted a primary care physician and was later referred to our tertiary hospital. She was first evaluated in April 2023 due to the described clinical presentation; however, she was lost to follow-up. She returned in July 2024 with a more noticeable increase in volume, limitation in cervical movements, and intermittent cervical pain, rated as 2/10 on the NPRS non-radiating, resolving at rest, and not requiring analgesics. She denied changes in voice, airway compression symptoms, dysphagia, B symptoms, or any other associated symptoms. Complementary studies were indicated. Vital signs: blood pressure 130/74 mmHg, heart rate 80 bpm, respiratory rate 20 breaths per minute, temperature 37 °C, oxygen saturation 95%, weight 50 kg, height 1.58 m.

On physical examination: Neurologically intact, asymmetrical neck with central trachea, left cervical region tumor approximately 20 × 12 cm, multilobulated morphology, firm consistency, adhered to deep planes, extending from the left mandibular angle to the middle third of the neck, with minimal pain on cervical movements, without skin changes, cardiopulmonary examination without alterations, abdomen depressible, without pain, and extremities without pathological data. (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Patient with a mass at the level of the left hemineck.

Complementary studies:

- Neck CT scan with contrast, dated 07/12/2024: left parotid gland with superficial lobe, oval-shaped tumor with lobulated, circumscribed margins, preserving the interface with adjacent tissues. Solid, hypodense, heterogeneous enhancement up to 60 HU, with some calcifications. Measurements: 92 × 68 × 118 mm in craniocaudal, anteroposterior, and transverse axes.
- Neck CT scan dated 03/31/2023: solid lesion in the submaxillary topography and left lateral neck, 70 × 57 mm, density 30 HU. Displaces the left sternocleidomastoid muscle and infiltrates the left submandibular gland. Normal thyroid. Vascular structures of normal morphology (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Coronal CT scan of the neck. Mass is observed at the left submandibular level.

Diagnosis: Tumor in the left lateral cervical region.

- FNAB dated 06/27/2023: lesion in the left submandibular region. Milan 4a. Pleomorphic adenoma.

Given the clinical and imaging findings consistent with the diagnosis of a left submandibular gland tumor, a complete surgical protocol was initiated. Laboratory tests were within normal parameters, and the patient was classified by the Anesthesiology Department as ASA I. Resection of the tumor dependent on the submandibular gland was performed on 09/13/2024. The patient was positioned in supine decubitus with neck hyperextension and right lateralization. An incision was made over the preauricular region of the cervical tumor, dissecting a skin flap up to the tumor border. Circumferential dissection of the tumor was performed, achieving hemostasis with energy devices, preserving the external and internal jugular veins, the sternocleidomastoid muscle, continuing dissection toward the mandibular border, locating and preserving the facial artery and vein. The left submandibular

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gland was dissected, hemostasis achieved, and the tumor plus left submandibular gland were removed in a single surgical specimen. Irrigation was performed with sterile solution and hemostasis verified with bipolar energy, confirming the absence of bleeding, complete textile count, placement of a 1/8-inch Drainovac, exteriorized on the anterior cervical face, resection of redundant skin, and closure by planes starting with the myofascial flap with 2-0 absorbable sutures and 5-0 non-absorbable sutures for subdermal stitches (Figure 3 and 4).

Figure 3. Evolution of surgical resection.

Figure 4. Left cervical region after tumor resection. Adjacent neurovascular anatomical structures were preserved.

Intraoperative findings: 20 cm tumor dependent on the left submandibular gland, with heterogeneous solid and cystic components, loosely adhered to adjacent structures (external and internal jugular veins, facial artery and vein, sternocleidomastoid muscle, prethyroid muscles), without lymphadenopathies suggestive of metastasis, with a normal left parotid gland (Figure 5).

FIGURE 5. Surgical specimen. Tumor measuring 20 cm in diameter from the left submandibular gland with a heterogeneous solid and cystic component.

On the first postoperative day, the patient was in good general condition, with tolerance to a liquid diet as accepted, without nausea or vomiting, afebrile, mild pain at the surgical site rated as 3/10 on VAS, controlled with analgesics and anti-inflammatory drugs, adequate diuresis, and no other symptoms.

Directed physical examination: asymmetrical neck with central trachea, surgical wound in the left cervical region, approximated, without signs of active bleeding, drenovac with 50 cc of hematic residue since surgery. Given the favorable postoperative evolution and absence of complications, the patient was discharged with follow-up appointments in the digestive and endocrine surgery outpatient clinic of a tertiary hospital. At one week postoperative control, she continued in good general condition, with pain at the left submandibular surgical site rated as 2/10 on VAS, no signs of systemic inflammatory response, tolerance to a complete diet, absence of dysphagia, and no limitation to mouth opening. Directed physical examination: wound in the left hemineck, approximated, without dehiscence, with scant serohematic residual drainage; the drain was removed.

At her second follow-up visit, six weeks postoperative, the patient continued to evolve favorably, with no pain, fever spikes, or signs of systemic inflammatory response, presenting the histopathological report: pleomorphic

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adenoma, size 16 × 9 × 8 cm, without identifying residual normal parenchyma.

Due to the satisfactory postoperative evolution and benign histopathological report with no evidence of malignancy, the patient was definitively discharged from digestive and endocrine surgery.

DISCUSSION

Salivary gland neoplasms mainly affect the major salivary glands (parotid, submandibular, and sublingual) and, to a lesser extent, the minor salivary glands. In our hospital and the population we serve, the incidence of these tumors is similarly low. Salivary gland tumors account for approximately 5% of head and neck neoplasms and only 0.6% of all tumors in the human body (1,4,5,7,8). Globally, the annual incidence of salivary gland-origin tumors is reported to be more than 0.5% of all malignant neoplasms (1,3). In Mexico, studies report an average incidence of 41% for malignant tumors and 66% for benign ones (8). Most patients with malignant salivary gland tumors are in their sixth or seventh decade of life, with a slight female predominance findings consistent with the present case (10).

Of the major salivary gland tumors, approximately 80% are benign. In contrast, 35–80% of minor salivary gland tumors are malignant, with great variability in their clinical and histopathological presentation (14). Parotid gland tumors represent 70–80% of all salivary gland tumors; 80% of these are benign and 20% are malignant. Submandibular gland tumors account for 10–15% of cases, with 50% being benign. Sublingual gland tumors represent only 1% of salivary gland neoplasms, of which 80% are malignant (10,11,14). Minor salivary gland tumors account for less than 1% of cases.

Histopathologically, 5 out of 10 submandibular gland tumors are benign, as confirmed in our case. Two main theories have been proposed to explain the origin of these neoplasms: the bicellular stem cell theory, suggesting that tumors arise from reserve cells of the excretory duct or intercalated duct cells, and the multicellular theory (4). Other suggested contributing factors include immunosuppression, history of Hodgkin's disease (increasing the risk fourfold), synchronous cancers such as medulloblastoma or basal cell carcinoma, infections including CMV, poliovirus, HPV types 16 and 18, Epstein-Barr virus, ionizing radiation, and occupational exposures such as asbestos mining, rubber manufacturing, woodworking, or plumbing (1,3,4). However, none of these factors were present in our patient.

Most benign salivary gland tumors appear as smooth, well-defined, mobile, slow-growing, painless masses. They may persist for years or even decades before patients seek medical attention (1,4,5). If left untreated, they may reach considerable size and cause facial disfigurement, as occurred in our case, where the tumor evolved over seven years with exponential growth in the last year. Rapid growth is considered a poor prognostic indicator. However, our patient did not present other concerning features such as nodularity,

irregular margins, infiltration, ulceration, pain, or neurological involvement. The initial diagnostic evaluation includes imaging studies such as ultrasound, CT, and/or MRI to determine size, location, lymphadenopathy, vascularity, and relationship with surrounding structures (6,7,8). FNAB is essential to determine the tumor lineage and to inform surgical planning. According to both national and international literature, pleomorphic adenoma is the most common salivary gland tumor—accounting for 60–70% of parotid neoplasms, 40–60% of submandibular tumors, and 40–70% of minor salivary gland tumors (11,12,13). The Milan System for Reporting Salivary Gland Cytopathology (MSRSGC) classifies FNAB findings by risk of malignancy and therapeutic recommendation. In our patient, CT showed a 20 cm mass in the left submandibular region with preserved interfaces and no vascular invasion, though with displacement. FNAB classified the lesion as Milan 4a: benign neoplasm, with a 4% risk of malignancy (9). Given the tumor's size, recent rapid growth, vascular displacement, and disfigurement, surgical resection was indicated (11,13).

Surgical excision is the treatment of choice for salivary gland tumors, although the approach depends on tumor type, size, staging, and patient condition. Facial nerve branches should be preserved unless involved. In small, low-grade tumors confined to the parenchyma, submandibular gland excision alone may suffice (1,4,3). In other cases, a more extensive resection is warranted, potentially including adjacent structures or regional lymph nodes (levels I–III). Tumors encasing the facial nerve may require resection with postoperative radiotherapy. When direct nerve repair is not feasible, nerve grafting using the great auricular or sural nerve may be performed. Skin involvement may require local or regional flaps or free tissue transfer (4,15).

Lymph node metastasis rates are low (14–20%), more common in high-grade or T-advanced tumors, or in those with extracapsular spread or facial paralysis. Clinically node-positive patients undergo neck dissection. For submandibular gland cancers, levels I–III are dissected; for parotid cancers, levels IB, II, III, IV, and VA are included (1,3,4,5,15).

In our patient, surgical treatment involved complete excision of the submandibular mass, approximately 20 cm in diameter. No neural or lymphatic involvement was observed intraoperatively, only vascular displacement. Complete resection was achieved with preserved dissection planes. The final histopathology report confirmed a benign pleomorphic adenoma, consistent with FNAB findings.

An important aspect of this case is the long delay in medical evaluation and definitive treatment. Although pleomorphic adenoma is typically benign, prolonged persistence without surgical intervention increases the risk of malignant transformation into carcinoma ex pleomorphic adenoma, reported in up to 6% of cases. Risk factors for malignant transformation include tumor size greater than 6 cm, evolution of more than 10 years, older age, and prior recurrence. Local recurrences occur in 70% of cases within

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three years. Thus, postoperative follow-up is crucial. International guidelines recommend the following surveillance schedule for benign neoplasms (3,15).

- Year 1: every 1–3 months
- Year 2: every 2–4 months
- Year 3: every 3–6 months
- Years 4–5: every 4–6 months
- After 5 years: annually

Malignant salivary gland neoplasms require at least 20 years of follow-up to assess outcomes (15).

CONCLUSION

Given its low incidence, submandibular gland neoplasms must be considered in the differential diagnosis of any painless cervical growth, especially those without signs of inflammation or systemic inflammatory response. While salivary gland tumors predominantly occur in the parotid gland, malignancy rates are notably higher in the submandibular and minor salivary glands. The probability of malignancy is inversely proportional to the size of the gland involved.

In the present case, the tumor developed in a female patient in her sixth decade of life, with an initial slow growth pattern over seven years, accelerating markedly in the final year. Despite its large size and eccentric extension, the tumor remained painless and was not associated with changes in voice, skin color, compressive symptoms, or neurological deficits.

The medical approach was guided by both national and international clinical practice guidelines. Imaging studies, specifically computed tomography, identified a solid, hypodense, heterogeneously enhancing tumor with calcifications while maintaining clear interfaces with adjacent tissues. These findings were not suggestive of malignancy.

Fine-needle aspiration biopsy confirmed the diagnosis of pleomorphic adenoma (Milan 4a), with a reported malignancy risk of 4%. The Milan classification system has become an essential tool for risk stratification in salivary gland tumors, offering diagnostic reliability with over 90% accuracy when combined with imaging studies. This validated the indication for surgical intervention as the most appropriate therapeutic option to prevent recurrence or malignant transformation.

Surgical treatment consisted of total excision of the submandibular gland and the associated tumor. The definitive histopathological report confirmed the diagnosis of pleomorphic adenoma. Postoperative follow-up was conducted through the general surgery service, with the patient subsequently discharged for continued monitoring in her designated medical unit.

It is concluded that, although salivary gland tumors are rare in both international literature and our own experience, their management must be structured according to established clinical guidelines. Among these tumors, submandibular gland neoplasms rank second in frequency, with an

approximate 50% distribution between benign and malignant etiologies. Pleomorphic adenoma is the most frequent benign neoplasm, while adenoid cystic carcinoma and mucoepidermoid carcinoma are the most common malignant tumors.

Long-term follow-up is essential due to the high risk of malignancy in tumors arising from smaller salivary glands or because of potential malignant transformation over time. The surgical management of salivary gland tumors continues to be a subject of debate in the literature, as a balance must be struck between achieving clear oncological margins and preserving aesthetic and functional outcomes for the patient. Preoperative and intraoperative data play a key role in guiding the surgeon regarding the extent of gland resection, the decision to preserve or resect the facial nerve with subsequent reconstruction, and whether regional lymph node dissection is warranted to achieve optimal oncological control.

A multidisciplinary approach, integrating clinical assessment, imaging, and cytopathology, is essential for achieving an accurate diagnosis and an effective surgical plan. Both national and international literature emphasize that complete surgical excision, followed by long-term clinical follow-up, is crucial to minimize the risk of local recurrence and prevent malignant transformation of salivary gland neoplasms. The American Society of Clinical Oncology (ASCO) recommends patient follow-up protocols lasting between 10 and 20 years, depending on tumor type and risk factors.

This extended follow-up is particularly important given that pleomorphic adenoma can evolve into carcinoma ex pleomorphic adenoma in up to 6% of cases, representing an aggressive neoplasm with a poor prognosis. The prognosis of salivary gland tumors is determined primarily by histological subtype: high-grade tumors are associated with worse outcomes, while low-grade tumors, such as the one presented in this report, generally have a favorable prognosis.

Finally, although submandibular gland tumors are uncommon, they demand a proactive and precise clinical approach. Proper surgical planning based on clinical, imaging, and cytopathological criteria allows for the optimization of both oncological and functional outcomes, minimizing the risks of recurrence and complications. The experience described in this case emphasizes that the combination of early diagnosis, complete surgical treatment, and structured follow-up are key determinants in the successful management of these neoplasms, establishing this approach as a standard in specialized surgical practice.

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